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ADRESSING THE NEEDS OF MIDDLE SCHOOL FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS WITH LISTENING DIFFICULTIES

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***Annotation.** This article is prepared with a specific purpose of explaining the reasons of listening difficulties in middle schools settings through providing effective techniques to avoid and solve this problem in foreign language learning procedures.*

***Keywords.** Listening, listening comprehension, audios, videos, comprehension difficulty, modern approach.*

Introduction. Listening is seen to be a kind of skill that is crucially vital in Language Acquisition. The reason for that, in most parts of our days, we spend so much time on listening to an audial input, such as, speeches, talks, songs, podcasts, noise and etc. It means that in order to master a language, it is required to develop listening skill, since language learning requires listening to new information provided by instructors.

Evidently, there are four language skills, two (listening and reading) are receptive, other two (speaking and writing) are productive skills. Some teachers

and learners deem that it is a big difficulty to enhance productive skills, as students have to produce something new. Therefore, sometimes, it is problematic to improve listening skill because of less attention to it.[1]

Main Body. Current school education programs include teaching four language skills simultaneously, since they well realized that, the single purpose of language learning is communication. In the past, grammar-translation method was the main way of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions. School teachers highlighted the significance of grammar rules, meaning that, the lessons were about having theoretical part only. [2]In this way, students face the loss of enthusiasm towards learning a language because of tedious learning atmosphere. It means that, inappropriate teaching methods and techniques can hinder the interests of pupils, especially, in middle schools when pupils pave a path for bright futures through learning.

Coming to these days, learners-centred approach is widely used, as it can cover the instruction of all language skills in one lesson. This approach demands putting students to the stage of lesson by making them express their ideas, thoughts, feedback on peers' performance and so on. By this way, it is more effective to teach middle schoolers, for example, teachers provide an audial input, after listening students can discuss, share ideas and understanding with each other in pairs, groups or undividually. However, sometimes, it is a bit problematic to organize such an interactive lesson practices. [3]The reasons include:

- invalid tools(headphones, tv, computer - all types of educational technologies must be checked whether they are applicable or not)[4]
- outside noise (the location of educational institution is also critical, since in overcrowded areas, it is a daunting task to organize listening activities)
- unknown words(school teachers are required to prepare tasks based on previous topics, in which pupils learnt new words by heart at home or during the lesson)[5]

In short, in order to avoid such problems deteriorating listening comprehension of middle schoolers, school government, teachers and students as well must take the responsibility of conducting an effective foreign language classess without technical, pychological and cognitive issues during the lessons.

Conclusion. To conclude, listening is a kind of skills that can be developed through well-prepared materials, well-organized lessons and enthusiasm to learn. Even though sometimes, it is a huge problem for some pupils to improve their listening comprehension in middle schools, they themselves, their teachers and classmates can aid to solve this matter by applying appropriate methods and techniques as well.

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